

Quantum Thermodynamics and Issues?

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Recently there has been interest in quantum thermodynamics which includes a Shannon's entropy term $S/(-k) = \sum_i P(e_i) \ln(P(e_i))$ where e_i is an energy level (e.g. see (1)). Quantum systems usually contain very few particles, yet the expression for Shannon's entropy derived from either the \ln of a factorial counting approaches or information theory explicitly depends on N being large. A thermodynamic approach using $dE=TdS$ with $E=\sum_i e_i$ and $dP(e_i)$ has an exact solution regardless of N of $P(e_i)=C(T)\exp(-e_i/T)$ with $S/(-k) = \sum_i P(e_i)\ln(P(e_i))$ if one assumes linearity i.e. $S=S_1+S_2$ with 1 and 2 representing two identical systems. Thus there seems to be an issue. Statistical mechanical calculations using $\exp(-e_i/T)$ probabilities have been frequently done for small systems (e.g. nuclei with 200 nucleons etc). In (1), a single particle two level system is analyzed using $P(e_i)=C(T)\exp(-e_i/T)$ which seems to imply that this form is mainly being imposed on the solution of T .

A second issue is that one has entropy for a pure quantum bound state which we suggest is : $S= S_p(n)+S_x$ (for a particle in a box with infinite potential walls). If one applies thermodynamics to describe a transition from level $n=1$ to level $n=2$ then there is large change in energy relative to the energy of level 1, yet one has initial and final entropies. If n is large then dn/n becomes small and one might consider $dE=TdS$, but the internal entropy and E depend in different ways on n . E is proportional to nn/LL while for a particle in a box $S_p(n)$ approaches a constant. If one considers a S_p as dropping as $1/n$ (as an example) then T temperature would need to be proportional to nnn/LL . If on the other hand, one considers a two level quantum system, one uses $P(e_i)=C \exp(-e_i/T)$. Internal entropy does not appear at all and there is a different T value with $S/(-k)= \sum_i P(e_i)\ln(P(e_i))$. This we argue brings into question the physical meaning of T and entropy. We try to resolve this by considering different solutions to $dE=TdS$ for $dW=0$

Large N Limit

If one considers different arrangements of a system with $n(i)$ instances of i , writes $B= \ln\{ N! / \text{Product over } i \ n(i)! \}$ and uses Stirling's approximation $\ln(N!) \approx N \ln N$ then:

$B \approx \text{constant} - \sum_i n(i)\ln(n(i))$ ((1)) with the second term representing entropy.

We note two things. First, the entropy result is an approximation which is only expected to hold in the high N situation. Secondly the \ln function is used because of the preexisting form of Stirling's approximation. Thus entropy contains \ln because Stirling's approximation contains \ln . Furthermore this approach gives physical significance to "arrangements". Finally we note that this derivation of entropy does not make use of the first law of thermodynamics.

It is interesting to note that the form of Shannon's entropy ((1)) may be obtained exactly (no approximation) without regard to the value of N if one uses the first law of thermodynamics with $dW=d\text{Work}=0$. In that case:

$dE=TdS$ ((2)) if one defines $dE= \text{Sum over } i \text{ } e_i dP(e_i)$ and wishes to write S only in terms of $P(e_i)$ then:

$S = - \text{Sum over } i \text{ } P(e_i) F(P(e_i))$ such that F is the inverse function of P . This gives no information about the specific form of $P(e_i)$. One may, however, make the assumption that if one has two identical systems with the same T then $P(e_{i,1}, e_{i,2}) = P(e_{i,1})P(e_{i,2})$. In such a case;

$E_{ave} = \text{Sum over } i \text{ } (e_{i,1}+e_{i,2})P(e_{i,1})P(e_{i,2})$ (other expressions yielding the same result may be written mixing i and j).

Thus one has linearity and expects that $S=S_1+S_2$. In such a case:

$$S = - \text{Sum over } i \text{ } P(e_i) \ln(P(e_i)) \quad ((3))$$

Furthermore an immediate solution is: $P(e_i) = C \exp(-e_i/T)$.

Formally this solution satisfies $dE=TdS$ with $dE=\text{Sum over } i \text{ } e_i dP(e_i)$ and so $P(e_i)$ maximizes entropy, subject to a constant average energy constraint, but the first law of thermodynamics ($dW=0$) already requires this. Following this approach ((3)) holds for any N and is not an approximation.

Linearity and the Case of Collisions

The approach of ((3)) (i.e. no approximations, no large N) is similar to imposing a balance of an elastic reaction with its time reversed scenario in a gas i.e.

$$E_1 + e_2 = e_3 + e_4 \quad \text{an } f(e_1)f(e_2)=f(e_3)f(e_4) \quad ((4))$$

Taking \ln of the second equation and equating it to the first, yields $f(e_i)=C \exp(-e_i/T)$ without any notion of entropy. One does not see the appearance of large N here, but it may be noted that $f(e_i)$ is the probability for a particle to be in a state e_i . The solution $C \exp(-e_i/T)$ assumes that $e_i \rightarrow$ infinite because ((4)) does not contain a constraint on total energy in the system. Thus, ((4)) is an approximate result. Furthermore ((4)) represents an average scenario with $f(e_i)N$ particles with energy e_i . In reality at any instant in time the only constraint is that $\text{Sum over } i \text{ } e_i n_i = E_{total}$ where n_i is the number of particles with energy i at this instant. $f(e_i)$ is the average over time of n_i , in other words there are fluctuations in a gas which are experimentally measurable it seems.

The restrictions just listed imply an approximate scheme for $\exp(-e_i/T)$, but ((3)) implies an exact result. For example, one may apply ((3)) to a quantum particle in a box with two energy levels $n=1$ and $n=2$ as done in (1). In such a case:

$$P(1) = 1/[1 + \exp(-3b/T)] \quad \text{where } b \text{ is proportional to } 1/LL \quad ((5))$$

This assumes that $P(1) = C \exp(-e_1/T)$ which by the first law of thermodynamics $dE = TdS$ is a solution which maximizes S , but also allows for $S = S_1 + S_2$ and $E = E_1 + E_2$ if 1 and 2 represent two identical noninteracting systems. What is T ? It is linked to E_{ave} , but this is not a fixed value. In other words, different values of T yield different values of $P(1)$ and of E_{ave} .

Maximization of Disorder?

The factorial function $(n!)$ counts arrangements which yield a constant average energy. If one takes \ln of this function, uses Stirling's approximation to obtain Shannon's form and then maximizes with the constraint $\sum e_i dP(e_i)$, one obtains $f(e_i) = C \exp(-e_i/T)$. This suggests a physical principle of maximum number of arrangements. Using the first law of thermodynamics with $dW = 0$ yields the exact result $S = -\sum_i P(e_i) \ln(P(e_i))$ for $dE = TdS$ with $dE = \sum_i e_i dP(e_i)$. An exact solution is $P(e_i) = C \exp(-e_i/T)$.

Is it possible to find another solution? Consider the entropy of the pure quantum state: $S = S_p(n) + S_x$ for a particle in a box with infinite potential walls. Then one has a corresponding $P_i(x) = W_i(x) W_i(x)$ ($W_i(x) = \sum_p a(p) \exp(ipx)$ = wavefunction) and $P_i(p) = a(p) a(p)$. If one uses Shannon's form:

$$S/(-k) = \sum_i \int dp dx P(e_i) P(p) P(x) \ln\{P(e_i) P(p) P(x)\}$$

$$= \sum_i P(e_i) \ln(P(e_i)) + \sum_i P(e_i) \{S_p(i) + S_x\} \quad ((6))$$

For simplicity consider the two level problem as in (1) with $a = P(1)$ and $1-a = P(2)$. Then using $dE = TdS$:

$$-e_1 + e_2 + TS_1 - TS_2 = \ln(a/(1-a)) \quad ((7)) \text{ with } e_1, e_2, S_1 \text{ and } S_2 \text{ given}$$

This has the solution: $a = 1/(1 + \exp(-B))$ where $B = -e_1 + e_2 + TS_1 - TS_2$ ((7))

Only experiment may determine if this alternative solution is appropriate, but we argue that the possibility exists. Thus, a solution of $dE = TdS$ using Shannon's entropy is not necessarily unique.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we consider some issues which may possibly be linked to quantum thermodynamics (or on the other hand the view of classical statistical mechanics).

Classical statistical mechanics assumes that Shannon's form of entropy follows from a large N approximation i.e. a factorial counting of arrangements followed by the use of Stirling's approximation. Alternatively, information theory probabilistic calculations of entropy also assume that if one has $P(e_i)$ then e_i appears $NP(e_i)$ times only if N is very large. If on the other hand one uses $dE = TdS$ for $dW = 0$ with $dE = \sum_i e_i dP(e_i)$ and wishes to have a linear S i.e. $S = S_1 + S_2$ if one uses $P_1(e_i) P_2(e_i)$, where 1 and 2 denote two identical systems at the same T

then an immediate and exact solution is $S = -\sum_i P(e_i) \ln(P(e_i))$ with $P(e_i) = C \exp(-e_i/T)$ also being exact. For example this approach is used for a single particle two level quantum system in (1). We argue in this note, however, that $\exp(-e_i/T)$ is not the only solution of $dE = TdS$ ($dW=0$). One may consider Shannon's form, but use $P(e_i)P_i(x)P_i(p)$ where $P_i(x) = W(x)W(x)$ wavefunction square for the bound i th state ($P_i(p) = a(p)a(p)$). This leads to a different form for $P(e_i)$ than $1/(1 + \exp(-(e_2 - e_1)))$ for the two level system, namely: $1/\{1 + \exp[e_1 - e_2 - TS_1 + TS_2]\}$. Experiments may determine if this or another form holds.

References

1. Abe, S. and Okuyami, S. Similarities Between Quantum Mechanics and Statistical Mechanics: Entropy, Temperature and Carnot Cycle
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